

Public Policy as an Instrument of Socio-economic Development; in the Context of MGNREGA

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Abstract

The developing countries suffer from various reason most of them the major problems is that Poverty & unemployment. As per the report of the Govt. of India a large sclae of population is Below poverty level and their social and economic status is very poor. So, the Policy - makers in India have decided & also realized that the need for generating employment opportunities on large scale in India. The Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act, 2005 has ensures 100 days of work in a monetary year to any poor family. MGNREGA Act was a blessing for rural poor people for the new job guarantee and a wage assurances for their life. It seems to be the new door open at grassroots level rural poor unskilled worker and the other hand they were participating the local administration with their unconsciousness. In this study we have tried to analysis the socio-economic condition of rural poor worker and how to developed their Socio - economic positions & upliftment this sections.

Keywords Rural Workers, Wages, Employment, Socio-Economic, MGNREGA.

Introduction

India has faces the two major problems one is Poverty and other is unemployment. The economic growth is not possible without job creation and income growth. India's population is most vulnerable to Socio-economic backwardness. The lack of job opportunity they become excessively dependent on agricultural sectors. India has a long history of work schemes in which the central and state government work for the safety of livelihoods in rural areas by providing employment. The country's previous policies and employment schemes outreach and fail to address the issues and have no significant impact so far. Therefore, the world's most prominent Employment Guarantee Act aimed directly for improving rural livelihood is Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA). The present study analyses the socio-economic evaluation through the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA). The MGNREGA scheme has the inherent advantage of ensuring that only those who are in need and who are willing to do manual labour become its beneficiaries. Wage workplace programs have a long history and review of these programs appear to be problematic. Low participation action for MGNREGA accession program, misidentification of beneficiaries, full planning of bureaucracy consumers, no participation of those communities in participation time, for doing less than household control, Many greedy, deceitful contractors, paying minimum wages - some chronic problem. Consequently, in this study an attempt has been made to identify the problems and solve them quickly.

Objective of study

The objectives of the study are -

1. Research area for economic evaluation and results of MGNREGA.
2. How far MGNREGA is taking place at the grass root level is a matter of discussion.
3. To elicit thoughts and ideas of beneficiaries about MGNREGA.
4. To study the socio-economic status of MGNREGA and its impact on the Indian economy.

5. To examine what remedial measures are taken in rural areas to ensure its effectiveness.
6. To see if this benefit is available to the rural area eligible claimants in this participation.

Review of Literature

Ashutosh Vyas in his book "Sociological Analysis of MGNREGA"(2018) traces the Rural development is a multi-dimensional concept, which involves all kinds of development in rural area through collective governmental efforts. Rural development has emerged as a strategy designed to improve the economic and social life of the people in rural areas. In this context The Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) is a revolutionary step for India's poor people. Since Independence, it was being demanded that right to work should be included in the list of fundamental rights. It was a matter of concern for all governments that inspite of their best efforts, the problem of unemployment and poverty never come under control. Therefore the MGNREGA is to enhance the livelihood security of people in rural area by generating wage employment through works and develop the infrastructure base of that area. N.P.Abdul Azeez & S.M.Jawed Akhtar in his book "Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA): Provisions, Implementation & Performance" in 2015 highlighted with the approach for an employment-centered development strategy, India's public employment programs are an integral part of the country's planning and policy. The Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) came into force in 2006 with the objective of enhancing the livelihood security of unorganized workers in rural areas by guaranteeing 100 days of wage employment in a financial year to rural households where members volunteer to do unskilled manual work. The Act further aims to create durable assets and strengthen the livelihood resource base of the rural poor. This book traces the origin and development of MGNREGA and analyzes its impact in India's rural areas in terms of the country's Millennium Development Goals, wage rates, financial inclusion, budgetary allocations, labor migration, governance, and environmental concerns. M.A.Beg, A.K.Tomar & Indu Varshney in the Book "MGNREGA: Empowering Rural Poor Through Wage Employment" in edited volume also highlighted the socio-economic development of the poor people in India throught this program. Moitri Dey in his book "MGNREGA: Success or Failure!" (2016), focus on this Act guarantees right to work by providing 100 days of guaranteed wage employment in a financial year to every rural household whose adult members are willing to do unskilled manual work. The enactment of the Act was a major achievement for Indian democracy. However, the real essence of the Act lies in its successful implementation of the Act.Dr. Dilip Kumar Ghosh & Dr. Debatra Dey also highlighted the needs of guaranteeing employment for poor in the perspective of above mentioned reasearch proposal in his book "Guaranteeing Employment : The case of MGNREGA in West Bengal" (2014). This books cover the essence of unemployment and poverty level of India in a present Scenario.

Government of India released "MGNREGA SAMEEKSHA" through the Ministry of Rural Development, MGNREGA is a flagship of the Government of India Rural Employment Scheme which was launched in April 2006. It is perhaps the largest and most ambitious social security and public works programme MGNGA's project is based on a number of issues, policies, societal and external decision-makers and analysts' perspectives. This is a readable summary of the members and concerns of this study. MGNREGA Survey to be a reference deterministic resource for stakeholders, academicians, journalists, civil society organizations, social and general readers.

Ashok Pankaj in his book "Inclusive Development through Guaranteed Employment: The MGNREGA Experience Ahead" (2023) includes the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (MGNREGS). It discusses the theoretical assumptions underlying the inclusive development of Employment Guarantee Scott (EGS), and draws on collective data and empirical experience with MGNREGS – the world's most inclusive candidate and university as an ambitious, rights-based development organization. Comprehensive workforce social security measures, local public works plots, and people-centered approaches to development. The book informs that the project is progressing, on the part of the parties it is an important part of the livelihood of the poorest of the poor, but the local independent institutions, which are entrusted with the project, are unable.

Area under Study:-

The present study focuses on the socio-economic evaluation through the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA). This study area analysis on purely the theoretical conception of Rural Panchayat areas beneficiaries under MGNREGA Act and their 100 days work-wage assurances and programme related challenges & preventing measures of the West Bengal in India.

Methodology

The proposed study is supposed to be based on a theoretical framework with some historical and empirical findings. It is also based on secondary data and information. The source of data collection from many books, journals, articles, Govt.data & information , e - newspaper & internet websites e.t.c.

Analysis

MGNREGA: Basic Features:-

1. Adult unskilled members of rural households willing to work may apply for employment.
2. It focuses on and guarantees 100 day jobs within a financial year
3. Job cards of the applicants will be issued from the Gram Panchayat Issuance Office within 15 days of application.
4. 100% cost of unskilled labor by Central Govt.
5. Although it supports 75% of the price in case of semi-skilled and skilled workers.
6. A 1/3 portion of the total benefits should go to women.
7. A sensitive social audit out of 6 months not exceeding.
8. Employment will be provided within 5 k.m.under the security system.
9. Payment of minimum wages by MGNREGA is work-related by Govt.
10. 150 secure jobs to be provided through natural calamities or droughts.
11. On the working site facilities like crèche, drinking water should be provided.
12. Provision for redressal of grievances should be made for the sake of legality and privacy.

Implementing Authorities & Agencies:-

It makes sure to dedicate the Employment Guarantee Assistant , the PO and the staff at the State, district, and Gram Panchayat level; for the execution of the scheme. It is authorized with the role to receive job applications. After receiving the applications, it is responsible for verifying them, all households are registered by the Gram Panchayat. The MGNREGS job cards are issued by the Gram Panchayat. It is responsible to allot work within 15 days from the application submission.It prepares an annual report that covers the achievement of the scheme. It holds Rozgar Diwas at every month. Gram Sabha monitors the work executed within the Gram Panchayat, It is the primary forum for social audits. It also works as a platform to resolve all workers queries related to any MGNREGA work. State Employment Guarantee Fund (SEGF) is established by state governments. It makes sure to dedicate the Employment Guarantee Assistant, the P.O. and the staff at the State, district, and Gram Panchayat level for the execution of the scheme.

Scope of MGNREGA:-

The central government disburses this amount to the states. The states then give these funds to local bodies, Gram Panchayats. All workers accounts are registered with Gram Panchayats. The works allocated in MGNREGA are directly linked to agriculture and allied activities. Tasks are mainly assigned to public works related to natural resource management, community or private resources, and general infrastructure. Gram Panchayats can undertake various types of authorized functions, such as;

- i). Block plantations on community land, planting trees.
- ii). Maintenance and construction of check dams.
- iii). Construction of farm ponds.

- iv). Water absorption trenches at footings to reduce soil erosion.
- v). Digging a mourning pit.
- vi). Restoration of irrigation ponds
- vii). Construction of Anganwadis, Village roads etc.

All these types of public works fall under the scheme. MGNREGA provides green and decent jobs. MGNREGA focuses on economic and social empowerment of women. Gramsabha is the main forum for wage aspirants to raise their voice and demand. Gram Sabhas and Gram Panchayats approve work shelves under MGNREGA and determine their priorities.

Impact on Indian Economy:-

With the implementation of MGNREGA, reports suggest that there have been significant changes in the social structure such as reduction in distress migration, higher participation of SC and ST population, improvement in their purchasing power, increase in average wages and economic empowerment of poor women, improvement in rural environment and sanitation, etc. Over the years, MGNREGA has caused a major financial drain on India's economic resources. The real benefits of this scheme do not reach the rural workers. In the process of fund transfer, there are many irregularities which cause the funds to shrink before reaching the beneficiaries. Article 243 (G) empowers a legislator to decide whether panchayats need to be empowered. But this provision sometimes makes it difficult to allocate funds. NREGA implementation has also been criticized for leakages and corruption. But with the introduction of the Direct Beneficiary Transfer (DBT) system introduced by the central government, where workers pay their money directly into bank accounts, the possibility of corruption has reduced significantly. For the financial year 2023-24, under sub-section (1) of Section 6 of the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act, 2005, the Ministry of Rural Development has notified the new wage rates. It will become effective from 1st April 2023 under the Ministry of Rural Development to revise the wages under MGNREGA.

MGNREGA Schemes Challenges:-

Although MGNREGA is a great scheme that works to benefit the rural population, it has some challenges -

- 1). Despite the maximum budget allocation for the MGNREGA scheme, the state government could not meet the continuous demand for employment due to declining GDP and lack of funds.
- 2). Another major challenge of this scheme is that the government fails to disburse money to workers within 15 days and often does not even compensate for late payment. As a result, workers started losing interest in work and MGNREGA scheme.
- 3). Due to lack of attention and inspection, many works allocated under MGNREGA scheme remain incomplete.

Preventing Measures:-

Village meetings conduct social audits to enable communities to monitor project implementation. It is a way of measuring, understanding, reporting and improving an organization's social and ethical performance. Also, it helps reduce the gap between vision, goals and reality. Other measures included below.

A). National Electronic Fund Management System:- At the Panchayat level, officials have been trained to use the electronic system developed by the National Informatics Center (NIC). NeFMS is meant to reduce the delay in funds for workers to meet their daily needs. Aadhaar card is linked so there is less chance of corruption. Under the NeFMS system, gram panchayats will pay workers within 48 hours of order generation.

B). Grievance Redressal Mechanism:- State level officials have been appointed to monitor grievance redressal in the state. Also, complaint boxes have been set up at the district level.

C). State Quality Monitor:- Government officials at the district level monitor the utilization of funds under this scheme.

D). National Level Monitor:- It consists of retired and serving government servants to monitor the policy and implementation of the program at the national level.

Conclusion

This Study explains impact on wider rural-urban settlements and rural livelihoods. It describes the progress towards MGNREGA in transforming rural India and empowering women. In this study, the impact of MGNREGA, qualitative changes in rural livelihoods and their development are measured. This study looks at the direct and indirect effects of employment opportunities, income growth and poverty reduction. Try to improve the welfare of rural households through minimum wage local employment. Villages are trapped by the poverty. Overpopulation, increasing unemployment and social unrest are causing for that. Improving individuals and households through increased employment and income. These aspects can enforce the rights of their family members. This discussion suggests that development in these areas can be helpful in improving empowerment and reducing rural areas such as study areas and dominance.

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